

Clustering and Prediction of the Employment Rate in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019

Istat defines the employment rate as the ratio between the employed and the population aged 15 and over.

The ranking of the employment rate in the Italian regions in 2019. Trentino-Alto Adige is in first place by value of the employment rate in the Italian regions in 2019 with an amount equal to 76.6%, followed by Emilia Romagna in 2019 with an amount equal to 75.4 and from Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 73.5%. In the middle of the table there are the Marche with a value equal to 69.8%, Umbria with an amount equal to 69.3% and Liguria with an amount equal to 67.7%. Calabria closes the ranking with an amount equal to 45.3%, Campania with a value equal to 45.2% and Sicily with a value equal to 44.5%.

Ranking of the Italian regions by change in the employment rate between 2004 and 2019. The region that in absolute value grew the most in terms of employment rate between 2004 and 2019 was Friuli Venezia Giulia with an amount equal to 5.5 (+ 8.36%), followed by Trentino Alto Adige with an amount equal to 5.4 (+ 7.58%), by Tuscany with an amount equal to 4.9 (+ 7.34%). In the middle of the table there are Emilia-Romagna with an absolute value of 3.7 (+ 5.16%), Lazio with 2.9 (+ 4.62%) and Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 2, 7 (+ 3.81%). They close the ranking of the regions that showed negative changes in the employment rate between 2004 and 2019, or that in the transition between 2004 and 2019 experienced a reduction in employment. These regions are Sicily, with an absolute value equal to -2.6 units (-5.52%), Campania with an amount equal to -4.2 units equal to -8.50%, and Calabria with a amount equal to -5.4 units equal to -10.65%.

North. The value of the employment rate in Northern Italy grew in the period between 2015 and 2019 from an amount of 69 to a value of 72.9 or a change of 3.50 units equivalent to 5.04%. Between 2015 and 2016 the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy grew from an amount equal to 69.00 to a value of 70.6 units or equal to a variation of 1.20 units equivalent to 1, 73%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the employment rate increased from an amount equal to 70.6 units up to a value equal to 71.5 units or equal to a variation of 0.90 units equivalent to a variation of 1.27%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the employment rate in Northern Italy grew from an amount equal to 71.5 units to a value of 72.2 units or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equivalent to a value of 0.98%. In the passage between 2018 and 2019 the value of the employment rate increased from an amount equal to 72.2 units up to a value of 72.9 units or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equal to an amount of 0.97%. However, the growth in the employment rate in the period 2004-2019 in Northern Italy was 20.45% higher than the value of the growth in the employment rate in the period 2015-2019.

Center. The value of the employment rate increased in the period between 2015 and 2019 in Central Italy from a value equal to 66 units up to an amount equal to 68.3 units or equal to a change of 2.50 units equivalent to a value 3.80%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of the employment rate in central Italy grew from an amount equal to 66 units to an amount equal to 66.5 units or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equivalent to a value of 1.06%. Between 2016 and 2017 the

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value of the employment rate in Central Italy grew from an amount equal to 66.5 units to a value of 67.2 units or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equivalent to a value of 1.05%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the employment rate in Central Italy grew from a value of 67.2 units to a value of 67.8 units or equal to a change of 0.60 units equal to a value of 0.89%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the employment rate in central Italy grew from a value of 67.8 units to a value of 68.3 units or equal to a value of 0.50 units equivalent to a value of 0.74%. However, the employment rate in Central Italy in the 2015-2019 period grew at a rate of 26.4% lower than the employment rate in the 2004-2019 period.

South of Italy. The value of the employment rate in the South increased in the period between 2015 and 2019 from an amount equal to 46 units up to a value equal to 48.5 units or a variation equal to a value of 2.40 units equivalent to a growth of 5.21%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016, the value of the employment rate in the South increased from an amount equal to 46 units to a value equal to 47 units or equal to a variation of 0.90 units equivalent to a value of 1, 95%. Between 2016 and 2017 the value of the employment rate in the South grew from an amount equal to 47.00 to a value of 47.70 units or equal to a variation of 0.70 units equivalent to a value of 1, 49%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of the employment rate in the South grew from an amount equal to 47.7 units up to a value equal to 48.2 units or equal to a variation of 0.50 units equivalent to a value of 1.05%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the employment rate increased from an amount equal to 48.2 units up to a value of 48.5 units or equal to a variation of 0.30 units equivalent to 0.62%. However, it is necessary that the performance of the employment rate of the South in the period 2015-2019 was 233% higher than the same performance in the period 2004-2019.

Clusterization. Clustering is then used to verify the possibility of a breakdown of the Italian regions by employment rate that may reflect the distinction between macro-regions. The clustering algorithm used is k-Means with optimized t-SNE representation by using the Silhouette coefficient. The analysis shows the existence of 3 clusters as indicated below:

- Cluster 1: made up of 4 regions namely Molise, Sardinia, Basilicata and Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: made up of 4 regions namely Sicily, Calabria, Campania, and Puglia;
- Cluster 3: made up of 12 regions namely Veneto, Tuscany, Lombardy, Piedmont, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Marche, Emilia-Romagna, Umbria, Trentino-Alto Adige, Liguria, Lazio.

Therefore, the result is a representation in which the regions of the Center-North are combined in a single cluster by employment rate while the southern regions are substantially divided into two clusters.

Machine Learning and Predictions. Machine learning algorithms were used to predict the 2019 occupancy rate value using data from the same 2004 variable. A comparison was made between the following algorithms:

- Tree Ensemble;
- Gradient Boosted Trees;
- Linear Regression;
- Artificial Neural Network-MLP;
- Random Forest;
- Probabilistic Neural Network-PNN.

The comparison between the indicated algorithms was made in terms of maximization of the r-square and minimization of error values. The sample used for learning was arranged in the measure of 70%.

The following indicators were used to evaluate machine learning algorithms in terms of predictive efficiency:

- R square;
- Mean Absolute Error;
- Mean Squared Error;
- Root Mean Squared Error;
- Mean Signed Difference.

The results show that the most efficient machine learning algorithm for prediction is Tree Ensemble.

Regression. Finally, a dynamic panel data model was created to estimate the trend of the employment rate in the Italian regions in the period 2004-2019. The results show that the employment rate is positively associated with involuntary part-time and with the average disposable income per capita, while it is negatively associated with the rate of non-participation in work and the rate of fatal injuries and permanent disability.

Conclusions. The employment rate in the Italian regions has tended to rise above all in the regions of the Center-North. However, in the three southern regions of Campania, Calabria and Sicily the employment rate decreased in the comparison between 2014 and 2019. The clustering analysis shows the presence of 3 clusters which, however, do not correspond to the Italian macro-regions. Rather, the clusters highlight the fact that the center-north is united in convergence towards high employment rates, while the southern regions are divided into two different clusters by differentiated value of the employment rate. Through the comparative analysis of various machine learning and prediction algorithms, the prediction of the 2019 occupancy rate value was made with 2004 data, choosing the "Ensemble Tree" algorithm as the best in terms of performance based on maximizing the R-framework and error minimization. Finally, the regression analysis shows the presence of a positive relationship between the employment rate and per capita income and involuntary part-time and the negative relationship between the employment rate and the rate of non-participation in work and the fatal injury rate. and permanent disabilities. In any case, the employment rate shows a slowdown in the growth rate both in the Northern and Central regions in comparison between the period 2015-2019 compared to the previous period 2004-2019.

Declarations

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